

UNIVERSITY OF SIEGEN

STUDY WORK

Evaluation and Compensation of the Effect of Dirt on Time-of-Flight 3D Imaging Systems

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June 29, 2021

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Abstract

In the past few years, 3D imaging technology has received a lot of attention. Time-of-Flight (ToF) cameras based on the indirect ToF principle calculate depth information by measuring the phase shift between the emitted periodic signal and the reflected signal. When the illumination from the modulated light source reaches the same pixel through multiple paths, multipath interference will occur. Acquisitions at multiple modulation frequencies are then required to separate the interfering paths. Parametric spectral estimation methods, such as Prony's method and its robust variants, have shown to succeed in resolving multiple paths from multi-frequency measurements. With the widespread usage of ToF cameras in various fields, the operating environment of the camera should be taken into account in order to obtain accurate 3D images. In this work, we aim to study the effect of dirt on 3D imaging systems quantitatively. To this end, ten sheets with different transmittances, between 50% and 100% are used. To the best of our knowledge, for the first time we provide standardized methods for evaluating the effect of dirt on protective covers in the depth estimation of "flash lidar". The accuracy of depth measurements obtained by multi-frequency multipath recovery in the absence of dust is up to 99%.

1 Introduction

With the development of digital imaging technology, cameras have been studied as the sensor of choice in a wide range of applications. Cameras are everywhere in modern society. 3D imaging technology has attracted more and more attention. 3D imaging systems can obtain the complete geometric information of natural 3D scenes, and use images with depth information to achieve accurate digitization of scenes, so as to achieve high-precision recognition, localization, reconstruction, scene understanding, and other key functions of machine vision. Marked by the release of Kinect in 2010 and iPhone X in 2017, 3D vision technology has changed from a high-end technology traditionally used only in professional fields to a consumer product.

Current professional or consumer 3D cameras use two mainstream techniques, Triangulation and Time-of-Flight (ToF) [1]. 3D vision techniques using triangulation include stereo vision and structured light technologies [2], and the basic principle uses triangular geometric parallax to obtain information about the distance from the target to the camera. This method has high accuracy at close range, but the error becomes larger rapidly with increasing distance. Compared with stereo vision and structured light solutions, the ToF scheme is relatively simple to implement, mainly including the transmitter and receiver. ToF camera modules generate an illumination control signal, which is used to drive a fast light source, so that it emits high-frequency modulated near-infrared light. After the light is scattered by the scene objects, the receiver calculates the depth information by the phase shift or time difference between the emitted light signal and the received light signal. The ToF technique is more stable in terms of error at different distances compared to triangulation. Most ToF sensors now use back-illuminated CMOS technology, significantly increasing the light-sensitive area and improving the photon collection rate. The response time can reach the nanosecond level, which can ensure high accuracy at long distances. The major ToF camera manufacturers include PMD, MESA, Optrima, and Microsoft [3]. ToF cameras are not only used in mobile phones, but also in many fields such as gesture interaction [4] [5], indoor surveillance [6], material sensing [7] [8], and automated driving [9].

In practical applications, ToF technology faces many challenges. Light is reflected multiple times in the target scene, and an object will reflect not only the modulated light emitted by the camera, but also light from other indirect paths. The interference between reflected light from multiple sources can lead to errors in depth measurement. This phenomenon is known as the multipath interference (MPI), which can affect the depth image quality of ToF cameras.

There are four general sources of multipath effects. First, the highly reflective objects in the target scene, for example, smooth walls, mirrors, etc. The second category is transparent objects or translucent objects, for example, glass. The third category includes corners and corner-like objects. Each point on the wall will generally receive reflected light from other points and will be partially reflected back to the camera. The last category includes the camera's internal lens system [10].

The complexity and variability of the real environment introduces a variable amount of uncertainty in the depth measurements. Weather (rain, wind, snow, fog, etc.) and dirt on the sensor cover are the most critical factors that affect the accuracy of the ToF camera [11]. In order to obtain accurate 3D images, the operating environment of the ToF camera should be taken into account. Therefore, it is necessary to study the effect of weather and dirt on the ToF cameras and the ways to overcome it.

2 Related Work

Since multipath interference is common, we review the research on multipath interference before studying the effect of dirt on ToF 3D imaging systems. The error compensation is performed by building an error lookup table in [12] [13]. This method has high accuracy, but the accuracy of compensation depends on the density of the error lookup table. The compensation time depends on the implemented scheme. On the implementation in [12], the compensation time is far less than the real-time acquisition time, which makes it possible to model the dynamic scene. In [14], two methods of multipath interference separation were introduced. The first method can separate two paths making use of four measurements at different modulation frequencies. The other method uses attenuation ratios to determine the amplitude and phase of up to two paths. In [15] a method combining ToF and structured light using the maximum likelihood approach to obtain accurate depth estimates is proposed. A multi-frequency-based approach to analyze multipath models that solves the problem by processing the temporal variation of the original measurements for each pixel in the Fourier domain was reported in [16]. The Multi-path problem can also be solved by *compressed sensing* (CS) [17]. Kadambi *et al.* proposed an approach to solve the multipath interference problem by recovering the per-pixel sparse time distribution expressed as a sequence of pulses. In [18] a sparse regularization method based on a CS framework is proposed to remove MPI. In [10], Bhandari *et al.* reported a sparsity-regularized solution, which uses multiple modulation frequency measurements to separate K interfering components. He reported a fast non-iterative approach based on parametric spectral estimation in [11], which proved that $2K + 1$ frequency measurements are necessary for decomposing K interfering paths.

Some publications exist that study the influence of the weather and dirt on the sensor. In [19] the influence of weather effects, in particular rain droplets, on distance and depth measurements with a ToF-camera-based sensor are examined based on optical simulation models [19]. Rain droplets cause a maximum position error of 15%. The impact of droplets on the propagation path and the impact of wet emitter surface through two simulation models were investigated in [20]. The results show that the effect of power loss due to direct beam-drop scattering is negligible, and there is minimum attenuation for various drop-to-beam ratios [20]. A ToF LiDAR under fog environment is present in [21] where performance is qualitatively and quantitatively investigated. A prediction model based on machine learning to the minimum fog visibility is introduced, which is trained on collected data. The impact of the

road dirt on the LiDAR is analyzed in [22] [23]. In [22] the dirt follows an almost-homogeneous distribution and leads to a maximal range decrement of 25%. Different levels of unknown transmissivity are obtained by sequential deposition of dust. In [23] the samples were collected in the real world. The transmission and reflection in two different positions were investigated.

However, the impact of dirt on 3D ToF cameras has not been studied so far. With the widespread use of 3D cameras, research on this topic has become increasingly significant.

3 Standardized Sample Preparation

3.1 Materials

3.1.1 Emitter and Receiver

In this study, we used a near-infrared light source as the emitter and the model ILH-IS01-94SN-SC201-WIR200 is shown in Figure 1(a), which contains SYNIOS® P2720 LED with a radiation angle of 120°. The peak wavelength is 940 nm.

The Thorlabs PDA10A-EC in Figure 1(b) was chosen as the receiver. This is an amplified silicon detector designed to detect light signals with wavelengths between 200 to 1100 nm. A buffered output drives 50 Ω load impedances up to 5 V.

(a) Emitter

(b) Receiver

Figure 1: Emitter with holder and receiver

3.1.2 Sheets

In this experiment, ten double-sided hard-coated polycarbonate sheets of 3 mm wide and A4 size were used to simulate sensor covers with different transmittances. Two fixed hooks were installed on the same side of the

sheet to hang them on mounting frames during the experiments and on shelf brackets when stored.

(a) Sheet

(b) Sheet hangs on the shelf bracket

Figure 2: Sheet with two hooks and hangs on the shelf bracket

3.1.3 Fresnel Lens

In order to accurately detect the effect of different dirt concentrations on the transmittance, two Fresnel lenses in Figure 3(a) were used. The emitter was fixed at the focal point of the first Fresnel lens, and we used the first Fresnel lens to obtain collimated light over a large aperture (preferably the whole

A4 plate) and the second Fresnel lens to focus the collimated light passing through the sample to a point where we placed the detector (Thorlabs' PDA100A-EC photodiode). The Fresnel lens model is ORAFOL's SC210. The SC210 has a focal length of 225.5 mm and an aperture of 257.6 mm and is suitable for A4-sized plates.

Figure 3: Fresnel lens and detail of the "sandwich" structure

To realize the aforementioned setup, we designed the "sandwich structure" in Figure 3(b). An A4-sized sheet was inserted between two Fresnel lenses. Note that the center of the A4 plate is aligned with the center of the Fresnel lens. The emitter and receiver are fixed on the focal points of both sides of the "sandwich" structure, respectively. Obtaining accurate transmittance measurements is a crucial prerequisite for the quantitative evaluation we aim for in this work. The two lenses are connected by four 3 cm long screws.

In Figure 4 the detailed geometry of the "sandwich" structure was illustrated.

Figure 4: The geometry of the “sandwich” structure. (a) Fresnel lens with 4 screws. (b) Top view of “sandwich” structure. (c) A4-sized sheet. (d) Top view of shelf bracket with sheet

Table 1: Main parameters of the “sandwich” structure

Parameters	Meaning
h'	Distance between top screw and bottom screw
d	Diameter of the Fresnel lens
d'	Diameter of clear aperture
o	Diameter of the screw
w^*	Length of the screw
l'	Distance between the top two screws
w_s	Thickness of the A4-size sheet
h	Width of the A4-sized sheet
l	Length of the A4-sized sheet
w	Thickness of the shelf bracket

A key point of the “sandwich” structure is the determination of the position of the four screws so that the center of the A4-sized sheet is exactly

aligned with the center of the Fresnel lens. Some equations are given to calculate the necessary parameters.

Figure 5: Screw coordinate system

Using the center point as the coordinate origin to establish the coordinate system shown in Figure 5. The $I_1(x_{i1}, y_{i1})$ point is the intersection of the clear aperture of Fresnel lens and the sheet, which can be calculated as follows:

$$y_{i1} = \frac{1}{2}h$$

$$x_{i1} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{2}d'\right)^2 - y_{i1}^2}$$

$S_1(x_1, y_1)$ is the center of the screw.

$$y_1 = y_{i1} + \frac{1}{2}o$$

$$x_1 = x_{i1} + \Delta x$$

Δx can be chosen at will as long as S_1 is on the lens. S_2, S_3, S_4 coordinates can be obtained by the principle of symmetry. The minimal length of the screw can be calculated through

$$w^* > w + w_s$$

The diameter of the lens is $d = 280$ mm, the diameter of clear aperture is 257.6 mm. o is 5 mm. A4 size is l (297 mm) * h (210 mm) * w_s (3 mm). w^* must be long enough so that the sheet can be inserted into the gap between the Fresnel lenses in Figure 3(b).

One would desire that all the light emitted by the emitter passes through the first Fresnel lens and the A4 plate, and is focused at the receiver by the second Fresnel lens. However, the actual situation is that some light only passes through the Fresnel lenses and do not passes through the A4 plate. This is the case, for example, for the light passing through the gray area in Figure 5. In order to block the interference of these undesired direct light path, we put an opaque black tape on the Fresnel lens corresponding to the gray area.

3.1.4 Voltage Detector

The receiver can convert the received optical signal into an electrical signal. An oscilloscope or digital multimeter can be used as a voltage detector. The chosen digital multimeter can be adjusted to different ranges and features better precision than the available oscilloscope. The precision of multimeter can reach 0.001 V, however, the precision of oscilloscope is only 0.2 V. Figure 6(a) shows the METRAHIT 27I multimeter chosen to detect voltage.

Figure 6: Digital multimeter and digital multimeter with oscilloscope

3.1.5 Spray Gun

In order to obtain homogeneously distributed dirt particles, we used a spray gun with different solution concentrations to spray the sheet. The spray gun is a model Wagner W550 SET.

(a) Wagner W550 SET

(b) Spray gun

Figure 7: Wagner W550 SET and spray gun

3.1.6 Optical rail

The optical rail is a 1m-long **X 95 profile**, a hollow, cylindrical aluminum profile with four lateral ridges that reinforce the system and hold the carriers [24]. There are three **Carriers X 95**, which can be utilized to mount components onto the **X 95 profile**. A Teflon film on the bottom side allows smooth gliding of the carriers on the X 95 rails and therefore provides a precise adjustment. The thumbscrews enable a flexible locking and unlocking of the carrier's position without additional tools [24]. Carrier ② has a support frame, like a shelf bracket, which can move back and forth and ver-

tically . Carrier ①, Carrier ②, Carrier ③, depicted in Figure 9, can move horizontally.

3.2 Methods

3.2.1 Setup

Figure 8: Sketch of the optical setup used to obtain the quantitative transmittance of the A4-sized plate. The emitter, the Fresnel lenses with “sandwich” structure and the receiver connected to the voltage measuring device are fixed on the optical rail from left to right.

Figure 9: Front and vertical view of real optical setup for obtaining quantitative transmittance of an A4-sized plate.

An outline of the setup is shown in Figure 8. The shelf bracket is placed on the middle carrier in the center of the optical rail. The holder with emitter is fixed on the focal point on one side, while the holder with receiver is placed on the focal point on the other side. The holder’s height was adjusted so that the center of the transmitter, receiver, sheet, and Fresnel lenses are in one horizontal straight line. The real-world setup is shown in Figure 9.

3.2.2 Spray

In this research, we aim to evaluate the effect of dirt on ToF cameras when operating outdoors, e.g., in automotive applications or mobile robotics. According to SAE J726 Rev. JUN93 [25], we chose *Arizona dust SAE J726 fine* as source of pollution. The dust is homogeneously mixed with water and the deposit of the spray gun is filled with the resulting mix. The polycarbonate sheets were used to simulate sensor covers with different transmittances. One of the sheets is completely clean, and its transmittance is considered as 100%. The transmittance of the remaining nine sheets was decreased by 5% each time, from 90% to 50%.

Consequently, the procedure for obtaining sheets with the desired transmittance values is a key point of this work. We took a similar approach to

that used by M.Trierweiler in [22]. The specific operation and measurement pipeline for obtaining a sheet with target transmittance T_d are as follows:

- 1) Prepare a mixture with appropriate solution concentrations: 10%, 17.5%, 20%. (For test purposes we prepared three solution concentrations)
- 2) Insert the blank sheet according to the above explanation in Section 3.1.3. Record the voltage V_o as a reference by digital multimeter.
- 3) Before spraying, the mixture must be mixed homogeneously and the spray gun must be warmed up. Adjust the nozzle of the spray gun until fine water particles is sprayed.
- 4) Spray the whole sheet thoroughly.
- 5) Wait until it dries.
- 6) Insert the sprayed sheet. Record the voltage V_i . The current transmittance T is $T = \frac{V_i}{V_o} \times 100\%$.
If $T = T_d$, stop.
If $T > T_d$, repeat the cycle of spraying from 3) to 6) until the $T = T_d$.
If $T < T_d$, erase the dirt, repeat the cycle from 2) to 6) until $T = T_d$.

Through the above method, we obtained a sheet with 100% transmittance and nine sheets with different transmittances between 90% to 50%.

3.3 Results

Using the above method, we got samples with reliable transmittance values.

Figure 10: The polluted samples with their transmittance.

For testing purposes, three different concentrations of the solution were used (10%, 17.5%, and 20%) to get samples with determined transmittance and evaluate the effect of dirt on a 3D imaging system. When the solution concentration is 20%, each spray resulted in a decrease in light transmission of more than 1%. Meanwhile, when the solution concentration is 10% or 17.5%, each spray affected the light transmission by less than 1%. Hence, a solution concentration of 17.5% was determined to use in this study in order to allow for fine adjustment of the transmittance.

At the beginning of the experiment, we used an oscilloscope as the detection device for the received voltage. However, since the low precision of the oscilloscope leads to the inability to detect fine adjustments of transmittance,

Table 2: Main parameters of the “sandwich” geometry

Sheet No.	Original/Final Voltage V_o (V)	Transmittance	Approximation
0(Ref.)	0.959 / —	100%	100%
1	0.954 / 0.858	89.9%	90%
2	0.974 / 0.832	85.4%	85%
3	0.962 / 0.774	80.5%	80%
4	0.951 / 0.711	74.8%	75%
5	0.968 / 0.667	69.6%	70%
6	0.961 / 0.626	65.1%	65%
7	0.950 / 0.575	60.5%	60%
8	0.957*/0.526	55.0%	55%
9	0.947 / 0.473	49.9%	50%

we abandoned the oscilloscope and replaced it with the digital multimeter (METRAHIT 27I). Although we can wipe off most of the dust on sheet No.8, which was used at the beginning to test the sensitivity of oscilloscopes and multimeters to voltage differences caused by dust variations, the sheet can not be restored to a perfect clean-state because of the possibility of remaining water stains and scratches caused by dust on its surface. This imperfect clean-state can lead to errors when measuring the original voltage. In contrast, the original voltage of the other nine sheets is measured with a clean surface. Consequently, the original voltage V_o of sheet No.8 is obtained by calculating the average of the other nine sheets. The original voltage V_o is between 0.95 V and 0.96 V except sheet No.6 with 0.974 V. The error of transmittance $\Delta T = |T_d - T|$ is under 0.5%. These Figure 10 are consistent with the notion that the more dirt attached to sheets, the lower was the transmittance.

3.4 Discussion

The original voltage V_o is nearly identical. This shows that the experimental setup is reliable, and the ten sheets have the same properties at the initial time. Compared to industrially-produced sheets with different transmittance, such as neutral density filters, our samples are more authentic and closer to the actual situation in a real-world environment. Special care must be taken at the beginning of the spraying, since just air or left-over droplets

of clean water in the nozzle may be projected on the sample if the warm-up phase of the tool is not carried out first. In such cases, already-deposited dust may be blown away and the transmittance may increase when spraying, instead of decreasing. The wind may blow down dirt on the sheet. High winds scrape away the dust on the surface, which is a regular occurrence in reality. Overall, the transmittance decreases as the number of spraying cycles increases. When the transmittance can be accurately determined, the relations between the sensor performance and the effect of dirt can be investigated qualitatively and quantitatively. These samples can be utilized on 3D imaging systems and other sensor systems, e.g., as a modification of [22].

Although we obtained sheets featuring specific transmittances, some challenges still remain to be addressed. First, the emitter has an opening angle of 120° , which is too large for the Fresnel lens, with a focal length of 225.5 mm and a diameter of 280 mm. Most of the light falls out of the clear aperture of the Fresnel lens, and only a small part of the light is collected through the lens. As a result, most of the energy is wasted, with the corresponding decrease of signal-to-noise ratio in the measurements. For this reason, we strongly recommend substituting it by another model with a 50° opening angle (New model: ILH-IN01-85SL-SC211-WIR200). Second, We chose the METRAHIT 27I multimeter instead of the oscilloscope. The oscilloscope has a 0.2 V resolution, which leads to a 2% error of transmittance, whereas the resolution of multimeter can reach 0.001 V. Third, theoretically, the sheet can be smoothly inserted into the Fresnel lens and hanged on the shelf bracket, but in fact, it is not easy. We removed two screws mounted on the Fresnel lens so that the lens can be loaded onto the shelf bracket from above. Last, throughout the measurement process, the sheets are frequently taken down and sprayed with fresh dust. Small differences between the sheet positions can make the obtained transmittance inaccurate. Consequently, it would not be possible to determine if the transmittance variation is caused by the effect of dust or the wrong location. Therefore, it is necessary to set a reference location point. Figure 3(b) shows a clip on the shelf bracket. The position of the clip is as a reference to ensure that the center of the Fresnel lens is aligned with the center of the emitter and receiver. In Figure 2(b) the blue line shows that the shelf bracket is not exactly horizontal. The left is slightly lower than the right. This error is negligible taking into account the error caused by the uncertainty of the Fresnel lens position.

4 Effect of Dirt on Time-of-Flight Cameras

4.1 Materials

4.1.1 ToF Camera

In this experiment, a “Selene” module from the company pmdtechnologies AG, with custom firmware is used.

Figure 11: A “Selene” module from PMD

One possible applications of the ToF camera is in material identification. This ToF module has been used in studies to identify materials in [7]. The ToF camera distinguishes materials by identifying differences in temporal impulse response. It was demonstrated in [7] that per-pixel material sensing by ToF sensors is possible. The “Selene” module was also used in the live demonstration [26]. In this demonstration, multiple paths for each pixel can be resolved.

4.1.2 The Polluted Sheets

We used the method in Section 3.2.2 to obtain sheets with homogeneously-distributed dirt. The sheets were numbered from 0 to 9 according to the

decrease of the transmittance. The transmittance sequence is [100%, 90%, 85%, 80%, 75%, 70%, 65%, 60%, 55%, 50%].

4.1.3 Panels

In this section four different experimental setups are considered for evaluation.

The White Board The first experimental object is a flat, clean, completely opaque white board.

Figure 12: White board on the right as the first test object

The Foam The sinusoidally-shaped foam, which looks like it is used for protection in packaging, has a surface that resembles a 2D sinusoid with an amplitude of 2.5 cm and a wavelength of 4.5 cm.

Figure 13: The sinusoidally-shaped foam

Four-square Target This target consists of a ground plane and three $5\text{ cm} \times 5\text{ cm}$ cuoids of different heights which are 3.5, 7, and 14 mm. Figure 14 shows the four-square targets. The upper-left square has four layers accounting for a total height of 14 mm. The upper-right square has one layer of 3.5 mm height. The lower-left is a ground plane. The lower-right square has two layers accounting for a total height of 7 mm.

Figure 14: The four-square target

Böhler Star A 3D form of Siemens star is used to determine the spatial resolution of the laser scanner sensor, which is an important parameter for ToF cameras [27]. The two Böhler stars we used are shown in Figure 15. If a sensor has good resolution, it can sharply retrieve the boundaries between the front and back fields of the Böhler star. The higher the resolution the smaller the unclear circle in the center [28]. The Böhler stars are both of 20 cm diameter. The left star features 48 fields, and the right one 24.

Figure 15: The Böhler stars are both of 20 cm diameter. The left star features 48 fields, and the right one 24.

4.2 Methods

4.2.1 Setup

The optical rail used in this phase is of the same material and construction as those mentioned in Section 3.1.6, but the length of this one is 1.5 m. The outline and real diagram of the setup are shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: The sketch of the setup for data acquisition and the real setup on the optical table in a dark room. From left to right are the ToF camera, the tilted shelf bracket and the target object.

The carrier with the ToF camera is fixed on the far left. The carrier with the experimental target is not fixed and can slide from side to side. The middle carrier has a shelf bracket that can be moved up and down and tilted as shown in Figure 17(b), on which dirty sheet with the desired transmittance is fixed. In order to eliminate the interference of other light in the experiment, the whole experimental equipment is in a dark room. The experiments are carried out on an optical table. The rail, the optical table, and the background wall are wrapped with highly-absorptive teddy cloth to reduce the interference due to uncontrolled multi-path effects.

(a) From left to right are the ToF camera, the tilted bracket, the hypothetical vertical bracket and target. The white solid line is the expected emitted photon path and the white dotted line is the expected reflected photon path. When the bracket is vertical, the short red dotted line is the reflected light path from the surface of the sheet. The long red dashed line is the path of reflected light from the surface of target.

(b) The dotted blue line only holds in the absence of dirt and supposing an ideal (non-diffusive) cover sheet. When the bracket is tilted, the paths of light, which reflected directly from the surface of the sheet, is also tilted, while the path of light reflected from the target surface is still horizontal and can be received by the receiver

Figure 17: The path of emitted light and reflected light for the direction orthogonal to the target surface, (a) hypothetically, when the bracket is vertical, (b) when the bracket is tilted.

In Section 3.1.6, we are not concerned about the emitted signal but only care about the received signal passing through the Fresnel lenses. Here, both transmitter and receiver are integrated into the ToF camera. Ideally, photons are emitted from the camera and then pass through the sheet to the target. Emission occurs at the target surface and the reflected photons pass through the sheet again and are received by the camera. Figure 17 shows the path of photons for the direction orthogonal to the target surface. The white solid line is the emitted photon path. The white dotted line is the ideal path of the reflected photon for the direction orthogonal to the target surface. Assume that the desired sheet is hung on a vertical bracket (dark gray vertical line in Figure 17(a)), the surface of a transparent sheet will reflect some of the light. At the same time, the light will also pass through the transparent sheet. The transmitted signal is reflected back by the target and superimposed with the reflected signal from the surface of the transparent sheet, resulting in multipath errors. The short red dotted line is the reflected light path from the surface of the sheet. The long red dotted line is the path of reflected light from the surface of the target. Compared with other reflected photons from

the target, the photons, which reflected directly on the surface of the sheet, have the shortest path. The reflected light can be of higher or lower intensity. This is due to the (close to) specular behavior of the sheet. Specular reflection means that photons get scattered back along a direction that forms the same angle with the surface than the incidence direction. This can “blind” an imaging sensor if such a sheet is placed perpendicularly to the line of sight of the camera. This phenomenon can also be observed in Figure 3 of [29]. In order to eliminate the influence of these reflections, we rotate the middle bracket in all evaluation experiments while observing the generated image until the “blind” area in the center of the picture disappears. As shown in Figure 17(b), the middle bracket is tilted and the dotted blue line only holds in the absence of dirt and supposing an ideal (non-diffusive) cover plate. The path of directly reflected light from the surface of the sheet is not received by the receiver, while the path of reflected light from the target surface can still be obtained.

We eliminated the effect of the strongest direct reflection from the bracket by rotating the center bracket, but this does not mean that the received signal is reliable. Light will be reflected and scatter many times in the scene. The signal received by each pixel contains multi-path reflected light, and the ToF camera faces the problem of multi-path interference (MPI), which leads to depth measurement errors.[27] [30] [11] [17].

4.2.2 Principle

The basic principle of the ToF camera is to emit light pulses to the observed object continuously, then receive the light pulses reflected from the object, and calculate the distance between the measured object and the camera by detecting the flight time of the light pulses. According to different modulation methods, time-of-flight methods can be generally divided into pulse modulation and continuous-wave modulation.

Pulse modulation requires not only high-frequency and high-intensity pulses to be generated at the transmitter side, which requires high physical device performance, but also high precision of time measurement. The sensors based on discrete pulse modulation measure the round-trip time of the optical pulse to calculate depth, while the sensors based on the lock-in principle measure phase shift between the transmitted and received periodic signal [1]. In this work, we mainly study ToF systems working in amplitude modulated continuous wave (AMCW) mode. Since the phase shift of the sinusoidally-modulated light is proportional to the distance of the object from the camera, the phase shift can be used to measure the distance.

Four Phase Algorithm We consider the case where only a single-frequency is available, namely, the mono-frequency approach. The mathematical representation of the original modulated light signal $s(t)$ and reflected signal $r(t)$:

$$s(t) = 1 + \lambda \cos(\omega t) \quad (1)$$

$$r(t) = A \cos(\omega t - \phi) + B \quad (2)$$

Here, λ is the modulation depth and ω is the angular frequency of modulation of the light source. A and B are the amplitude and intensity offset of the reflection, respectively. ϕ is the delay between the transmitted signal and the reflected signal. The relationship between the target and the camera is given by the following equation,

$$d = c\phi/2\omega \quad (3)$$

where c is the speed of light. A continuous wave time-of-flight sensor measures the correlation function between the two signals. A similar description of the ToF image formation model is also provided in [11] [29],

$$\begin{aligned} m_\omega(\tau_q) &= (s(t) \otimes r(t))(\tau) \\ &= \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2T} \int_{-T}^T [1 + \lambda \cdot \cos(\omega t + \omega\tau_q)] [A \cos(\omega t - \phi) + B] dt \\ &= \frac{\omega}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi/\omega} [\lambda A \cos(\omega t + \omega\tau_q) \cos(\omega t - \phi) + B] dt \\ &= \frac{\omega}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi/\omega} \left\{ \frac{\lambda A}{2} [\cos(\omega t + \omega\tau_q - \omega t + \phi) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \cos(\omega t + \omega\tau_q + \omega t - \phi)] + B \right\} dt \\ &= \frac{\lambda A}{2} \cos(\omega\tau_q + \phi) + B \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where \otimes denotes cross-correlation. In order to recover all the parameters, only three measurements are needed, although in practice four measurements are usually used. By using the “four-phases algorithm”, we can calculate the amplitude A , the phase shift ϕ , and the offset B . Using four samples at $\tau_q = \pi q / 4\omega$ with $q=0, \dots, 3$:

$$A = \sqrt{(m_\omega(\tau_3) - m_\omega(\tau_1))^2 + (m_\omega(\tau_0) - m_\omega(\tau_2))^2} / \lambda \quad (5)$$

$$\tan \phi = \left(\frac{m_\omega(\tau_3) - m_\omega(\tau_1)}{m_\omega(\tau_0) - m_\omega(\tau_2)} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$B = \frac{m_\omega(\tau_0) + m_\omega(\tau_1) + m_\omega(\tau_2) + m_\omega(\tau_3)}{4} \quad (7)$$

Therefore, the obtained values of amplitude and phase can be jointly represented by the following complex number:

$$Z_\omega = A e^{j\phi(\omega)} \quad (8)$$

Multi-Frequency Approach In the process of depth recovery, we calculate the phase shift between the reference signal and the incoming signal. When the illumination from the modulated light source reaches the same pixel through multiple paths, multipath interference will occur. However, the sum of several sine waves of the same frequency and different phases is just another sine wave of the same frequency and a different phase. The final result is that the camera sees the wrong depth measurement, which can lead to great error in depth and amplitude [29]. We focus on reflective MPI. Using multiple modulation frequencies is one of the main methods to solve the problem of mixed paths per pixel. We change the signal formulation from Eq.1 to complex form,

$$s(t) = 1 + \lambda e^{j\omega t} \quad (9)$$

The optical signal arriving at PMD pixels should be the superposition of several bounces so that it can be expressed as the finite sum of the shifted and damped versions of periodic illumination signals [17]. In phasor notation, for K components,

$$r(t) = c_0 + \sum_{k=1}^K A_k e^{j(\omega t - \phi_k(\omega))}. \quad (10)$$

where, c_0 is a constant, the phase delay corresponding to each reflection path K is $\phi_k(\omega) = 2d_k\omega/c$. $\{d_k\}_{k=1}^K$ and $\{A_k\}_{k=1}^K$ are the depths and amplitudes at which the corresponding reflection occurs, respectively.

Each PMD pixel records,

$$m_\omega^K(\tau) = c_0 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \sum_{k=1}^K A_k e^{j\omega\tau} e^{j\phi_k(\omega)} \quad (11)$$

$$= c_0 + \frac{\lambda}{2} e^{j\omega\tau} \sum_{k=1}^K A_k e^{j\phi_k(\omega)}. \quad (12)$$

Clearly, for a defined modulation frequency ω , $m_\omega^K(\tau)$ is proportional to $e^{j\omega\tau}$. The “four-phases algorithm” is not suitable for the calculation of more than one depth, because it supposes a single depth and retrieves a single amplitude and a single phase. Thus, it only makes sense for $K=1$. By virtue of the superposition principle, Eq.8 now becomes a sum of complex exponentials.

$$Z(\omega) = \sum_{k=1}^K A_k e^{j\phi_k(\omega)}. \quad (13)$$

In [31], a method based on an ℓ_1 -style global optimization has been proposed. In [32], Pati *et al.* introduced a recursive algorithm called orthogonal matching pursuit (OMP), which calculates the representation of signals with respect to arbitrary dictionaries of elementary functions. Bhandari *et al.* used orthogonal matching pursuit (OMP) in [10] to implement a multi-frequency approach for decomposing multiple depths observed by ToF camera. However, this CS framework is considered not feasible because it requires not only large memory requirements to store data but also complex calculations [17]. We use parametric spectral estimation methods, more specifically the *matrix pencil method*, which is a robust variant of Prony’s method (polynomial annihilation). This method was proposed in [33] and used to estimate the parameters of exponentially damped/undamped sine waves in noise. The method has been successfully applied in [11] and [34] for the depth super-resolution problem, which can be seen as the estimation of parameters for K complex exponentials, where K is the number of paths. In [11], Feigin *et al.* provide a closed-form, noniterative technique and proved that $2K + 1$ frequency measurements are necessary for decomposing K interfering paths. In [34], Bhandari *et al.* showed that the super-resolution problem in context of ToF imaging can be re-formulated as a finite-rate-of-innovation sampling problem. The results provided in [34] showed that the calculation efficiency of matrix pencil method is five times that of OMP.

4.3 Experiments and Results

4.3.1 Experiments

All experimental procedures were carried out in a dark room. The ToF camera is fixed at the far left end of the optical rail. We find an angle by manually rotating the bracket to avoid that the direct reflection from the sheet blinds the camera. The height of the camera and bracket is adjusted so that the light from the camera passes through the center of the sheet. The initial distance between the center of ToF camera and the panel is 50

cm. Between the camera and the panel one sheet is placed with the desired transmittance. The height and position of the camera and bracket are fixed. In our work, we present the results for mono-frequency estimation of a single path applying the four phases algorithm and multi-frequency estimation of several paths using the *matrix pencil method* as parametric multipath estimation algorithm. In multi-frequency estimation we consider two cases for solving the inverse problem. One is multipath for a single path, $K = 1$, and the same method for a two paths case, $K = 2$, (path P_1 and path P_2). We resolved multiple paths directly from multi-frequency data acquired at 7 equally-spaced frequencies from 0 to 120 MHz (20 MHz step size). The data acquisition process is shown below:

- 1) Place the first panel at a distance of 50 cm from the ToF camera.
- 2) Hang the sheets with different transmittance in sequence [100%, 90%, 85% ... 50%] and record the multi-frequency ToF raw data for each of them.
- 3) Slide the panel horizontally to the right 10cm each time. Repeat the previous step.
- 4) Repeat the above steps until the panel is placed at 140 cm of the camera.
- 5) Save data $D(i, q)$. $i, q \in [1, 10]$.

Figure 18: Flowchart: How to acquire data

We tested four different panels (white placard, the panel containing the sinusoidally-shaped foam and four-square target, and the Böhler star) following the above steps to acquire the corresponding data.

4.3.2 Results

The White Board In Figure 19 we show the case with a 100% transmittance sheet and the white board placed at 50 cm distance of the camera. The amplitude, phase, and depth images obtained applying the “four phases algorithm” at the minimum frequency $f_{min} = 20$ MHz and maximum frequency $f_{max} = 120$ MHz are presented in Figure 19(a) and 19(b). The results of multi-frequency estimation of several paths ($K = 1$, $K = 2$) are presented in Figure 19(c)-19(e).

Figure 19: With 100% light transmittance sheet, at distance 50 cm: The first row shows the amplitude plots, the second row shows the phase plots, and the third row shows the depth plots.

From Figure 19 we can conclude that the higher the reflected amplitudes,

the higher the depth accuracy. Low amplitude often appears at the edge of the image because the emitted light power decays radially, resulting in an overestimation of depth. In the case of a mono-frequency, i.e., $f_{min} = 20$ MHz and $f_{max} = 120$ MHz, the difference in depth between the central area and the corners of the both depth images is greater than 1 cm. In contrast, in the case of multi-frequency multipath recovery, whether in single path $K=1$ or multipath $K=2$ path P_1 , the difference in depth between the central area and the corners is less than 0.7 cm. Although there are two paths, P_1 and P_2 , in the case of multipath $K = 2$, path P_1 dominates. Therefore, in the subsequent discussion, we focus mainly on the case of $K = 2$ path P_1 , and path P_2 will not be mentioned.

Figure 20: The first row shows the 3D plots of the distance error versus transmittance error and distance. The second row draws the isolines plots of the distance error corresponding to the two-dimensional plane formed by the transparency and actual distance

As introduced in the data acquisition process, we are able to obtain $D(i, q)$ $i, q = 1 \dots 10$, which can be used to calculate the depth estimation via “four phase algorithm” for each frequency and “matrix pencil method” simultaneously using the data acquired at all frequencies. One of the main applications of ToF cameras is in autonomous driving, so it makes sense to search the relationship between depth measurement (measured distance), the distance between the target and the camera (actual distance), and the transmittance of the cover (dirt). The resolution of the ToF cameras does not change as the distance increases, the accuracy drops due to the lower amplitude (fewer incoming photons) as the distance increases. As the experiment progresses, the distance between the camera and the white board increases and the number of pixel points occupied by the plate decreases. We calculated the average value of ten points in the center of the white board.

The observation is consistent with the properties of the ToF camera. In the case of multi-frequency multipath recovery, the accuracy of the measured depth measurements in the interval of 50 cm to 140 cm is 99%- 99.7% when the sheet’s transmittance is 100% , regardless of the multipath $K = 1$ or $K = 2$. The accuracy of the ToF camera hardly varies with increasing distance. For distance in the range of 50 cm to 120 cm, when $f_{min} = 20$ MHz, the accuracy of the depth measurements by the single-frequency method reached 88.4%- 99.6%. At the same distance, the influence of transmittance on the depth measurements was compared. For example, at a distance of 50 cm, in the single-frequency approach way with $f_{min} = 20$ MHz, the accuracy of the depth measurements can still reach 80% when the sheet’s transmittance drops to 82%. However, in the case of multi-frequency multipath recovery with $K = 1$, when the sheet’s transmittance is 87%, the depth accuracy further drops to 80%.

Figure 20(e)-20(h) show the the isolines plots of the distance error versus transmittance and distance. We observed that the camera has a very low tolerance for dust. The distance error in the darkest blue region is less than 0.1 m, which leads to an accuracy of 80% to 99.7%.

Figure 21: 3D representation of the distance error versus transmittance and distance and the isoline plot of distance error. In the case of multi-frequency multipath recovery with $K = 1$, the images are divided into three parts by the red and white lines. These three parts are defined as the invalid work area, the unreliable work area, and the reliable work area.

Depending on the limit operating conditions of the camera in terms of varying light transmittance and distance, we divided the camera operation into three stages in Figure 21(a) and Figure 21(b). We defined that the area to the left of the red line is the invalid work area of the camera (the accuracy of the depth measurements is lower than 70%). The result of the depth measurements within this area is approximately equal to the distance between the camera and the sheet, i.e., about 20 cm, because the dirt on the sheet has blocked most of the light, either in its way to the target or in its return path after being scattered by the target. The area between the red and white lines is the unreliable work area of the camera (the accuracy of the depth measurements is between 70% and 90%). The accuracy of camera measurements in this area is significantly affected by dirt. The area to the right of the white line is the reliable work area of the camera (the accuracy of the depth measurements is higher than 90%). The depth measurements obtained by the camera in this area in the absence of dirt or at a short distance (within 50 cm) with a small amount of dirt (the transmittance is higher than 90%) are reliable.

The Foam In [35] several experimental setups have been proposed to compare the performance of different depth cameras. These experimental setups can be used not only for comparison between different cameras but also for performance analysis of the same camera under different conditions, for example, if camera lenses or protective covers are dusty. We used a similar experimental setup to the one used by Langmann et al. in [35]. In this stage

we focus on the foam inside the red square in Figure 22.

Figure 22: Test setup with sinusoidally-shaped foam and four-square target

This object has a surface close to a 2D sinusoid with an amplitude of 2.5 cm and a wavelength of 4.5 cm.

Figure 23: With 100% light transmittance sheet, at distance 50 cm: The first row shows the amplitude plots, the second row shows the phase plots, and the third row shows the depth plots.

From the above Figure 23, we can see that the single-path assumption yields invalid results for the foam target, whether using single-frequency method or multi-frequency multipath recovery. This is attributed to the unique surface structure of the measured object. Interestingly, in the case of multi-frequency multipath recovery with $K = 2$, the values measured through path P_1 and the values measured through path P_2 are complementary, i.e., points that were incorrectly measured from path P_1 were measured correctly from path P_2 . This experiment was not designed to measure exact values but to observe the sine wave on the surface of the foam. The single-path cannot accurately reconstruct the sine wave image, so a more accurate sine wave image can be realized by combining path P_1 and path P_2 .

Figure 24: Sine wave graphs obtained by combining path 1 and path 2. (a) With 90% transmittance at 50 cm distance. (b) With 100% transmittance at 90 cm distance. (c) With 100% transmittance at 60 cm distance. (d) With 100% transmittance at 140 cm distance.

In the absence of dirt, multipath interference has already appeared in the measurement of foam's unique surface structure. If dirt interference is added, the measurement results will be completely unreliable. In Figure 24(a) when the light transmittance is 90%, sine wave shape on the foam surface cannot be observed. However, when the light transmittance is 100%, the pattern can be observed. As the distance between the camera and the foam becomes longer, the details of the pattern become blurred.

Four-square Target This object is found in the central region of Figure 22. The four-square target consists of a ground plane and three 5 cm \times 5cm cuoids of different heights, which are 3.5, 7 and 14 mm. The four squares can be understood as four white boards. Therefore, the phenomena we observed in the whiteboard experiment will theoretically appear here.

Figure 25: Standard deviation at each distance in each square without dirt. 3 mm as the reference standard deviation with a solid black line. The colored solid lines with “+” are standard deviation for the case of multi-frequency multipath recovery with $K = 1$. The colored dashed lines with “ \times ” are standard deviation for the case of multi-frequency multipath recovery with $K = 2$, path P_1 . The colored dashed lines with “ $*$ ” are standard deviation for the case of single-frequency $f_{min} = 20$ MHz. The colored dashed lines with “ o ” are standard deviation for the case of single-frequency $f_{max} = 120$ MHz.

The standard deviations in the case of single-frequency $f_{min} = 20$ MHz, $f_{max} = 120$ MHz and multi-frequency multipath recovery $K = 1$, $K = 2$ were calculated respectively. In a single-frequency $f_{min} = 20$ MHz, the standard deviation in each square at each position is over 8 mm. Consequently, the surfaces of the four squares appear to be uneven. Take into account the scale, Having standard deviations of 2 or 3 mm is acceptable. Compared with the reference standard deviation, only in the case of multi-frequency multipath recovery with $K = 1$, the majority of the standard deviations are below 3 mm, which are the colored solid line in the Figure 25.

The Figure 26 verifies the conclusions we have obtained in the white board experiment. The effect of dirt on accuracy is very relevant. With the increase of distance, the boundaries of four squares have become increasingly difficult to distinguish. When observing the first row of the picture, the four squares can hardly be distinguished by the naked eye. Increasing the modulation frequency enhances the precision of depth measurements. The four square can be easily distinguished in the 120 MHz case. When multi-frequency mul-

Figure 26: Four-square target depth plots. The first row shows the depth images at 20 MHz. The second row shows the depth images at 120 MHz. The third row shows the depth images with multi-frequency multipath recovery with $K=1$. (a) With 90% transmittance at 50 cm distance. (b) With 100% transmittance at 50 cm distance. (c) With 100% transmittance at 140 cm distance.

tipath recovery with $K = 1$, the measured four squares are obviously clearer than those measured by single-frequency. This illustrates that the multi-frequency multipath recovery is preferable to the single-frequency approach even for a single return path. Nevertheless, when dirt exists, comparing the first and second columns, the 10% reduction in transmittance directly results in the four squares being indistinguishable.

In this experiment, we are mainly interested in the height difference between squares. We calculate the average of all pixel points within each square. Theoretically, without any interference $|\Delta D4| = 4 \times |\Delta D1| = 2 \times |\Delta D2|$, $|D1| = 3.5$ mm. The subscripts indicate the method used in the camera for the depth measurements. 20 MHz, 120 MHz and $K = 1$ represent the cases of single-frequency $f_{min} = 20$ MHz, single-frequency $f_{max} = 120$ MHz and multi-frequency multipath recovery with $K = 1$, respectively. Each square can be considered as a white board. therefore, the conclusions we obtained in the white board experiment also apply here. When considering only the case where the transmittance of the sheet is 100%, i.e., no dirt. In the case of single-frequency $f_{min} = 20$ MHz, the measured difference between the squares is significantly larger than the real value. Our results in the white board experiment showed that the accuracy of the camera is 88.4% – 99.6% in the 1.5 m range at a single-frequency $f_{min} = 20$ MHz. The error (5 mm) caused by the camera in this case is bigger than the difference $|\Delta D1_{20\text{MHz}}|$ and $|\Delta D2_{20\text{MHz}}|$. The height difference $|\Delta D4_{20\text{MHz}}|$ between the square containing four layers and the base square can be calculated almost correctly, except at a distance of 70 cm. In the case of single-frequency $f_{max} = 120$ MHz, the calculation of height difference is more reliable than in the case of $f_{min} = 20$ MHz, but $|\Delta D1_{120\text{MHz}}|$ is still inaccurate. $|\Delta D2_{120\text{MHz}}|$ and $|\Delta D4_{120\text{MHz}}|$ have improved significantly and both measured values are close to the real value, but both showed inaccurate values at 80 cm. In the case of multi-frequency multipath recovery with $K=1$, the height differences are all within a reasonable range. The accuracy of $|\Delta D4_{K=1}|$ is much higher than that of $|\Delta D2_{K=1}|$ and $|\Delta D1_{K=1}|$. The larger the real difference distance between two squares, the higher the accuracy of the measured difference.

When the camera works in unreliable work area, which is defined in Figure 21, the camera collects the inaccurate depth estimations. When two depth estimations with errors are summed or subtracted, following error propagation, the total error is the superposition of these two errors. Therefore, the total error is far beyond a reasonable error range. Most of the dark red areas in all subplots of Figure 27 are located in the unreliable work area. When the camera works in the invalid work area, the dust almost completely blocks the light, so the depth estimations acquired by the camera are mostly the distance between the camera and the sheet (about 20 cm). Consequently,

Figure 27: Height difference between squares: $\Delta D1$ is the difference between the square containing one layer and the ground plane. $\Delta D2$ is the difference between a square containing two layers and the ground plane. $\Delta D4$ is the difference between a square containing four layers and the ground plane.

the square height difference is almost zero. Most of the dark blue areas in all subplots of Figure 27 are located in the invalid work area.

Böhler Star A Böhler star is a device for measuring spatial resolution, which is a very important parameter for 3D cameras. The axial resolution r_{ax} can be calculated as

$$r_{\text{ax}} = \frac{\pi d_p M}{n} \quad (14)$$

where n is the number of fields of the star (here 48 and 24, respectively), d_p is the ratio between the diameter of the incorrectly measured circle in the middle of the star and the diameter M of the star. The diameter of both Böhler stars is 20 cm. From the axial resolution r_{ax} and the distance D between the camera and the Böhler star, we obtain the angular resolution r_{an} as

$$r_{\text{an}} = \text{atan2}(r_{\text{ax}}, D) \quad (15)$$

Figure 28: Depth images of the two Böhler stars. The first row shows for the case of a single-frequency $f_{min} = 20$ Mhz. The second row shows for the case of a single-frequency $f_{max} = 120$ MHz. The third row shows for the case of multi-frequency multipath recovery with $K = 1$. The fourth row shows for the case of multi-frequency multipath recovery with $K = 2$, path P_1 .

In Figure 28, some of the resulting images are shown when the camera works in the reliable area. Note that in single-frequency case $f_{min} = 20$ MHz, When the distance is 90 cm, an inaccurate area appears in the center of the Figure 28(c), i.e., the dark blue area in the center of Figure 28(c). At a distance of 140 cm, the axial resolution in Figure 28(d) can not be computed due to the expanding dark blue area.

(a) Axial resolution, 24-fields star

(b) Angular resolution, 24-fields star

(c) Axial resolution, 48-fields star

(d) Angular resolution, 48-fields star

Figure 29: In the case of multi-frequency multipath recovery with $K = 1$, axial resolution and angular resolution obtained using Böhler star with 24-fields and 48-fields, respectively.

With the help of Eq. 14, the axial resolution of the camera can be easily calculated when the unknown parameter d_p is determined.

K=1 depth image with 100% transmittance at 50 cm distance

Figure 30: P_{inc} is the number of pixels occupied by the diameter of an incorrectly measured circle. P_C is the number of pixels occupied by the diameter of a star.

In theory, the resolution measured via the 24-fields Böhler star and the 48-fields Böhler star should be identical under ideal conditions. In the case of multi-frequency multi-path recovery with $K = 1$, the obtained axial resolution of the camera using the 24-fields Böhler star is 0.2942 ± 0.0588 cm at a distance of 50 cm, which corresponds to 0.0059 ± 0.0012 degrees. However, the axial resolution obtained using the 48-fields Böhler star is 0.2647 ± 0.0441 cm, which corresponds to 0.0053 ± 0.0009 degrees. The angular resolution at a distance of 70 cm is 0.0125 ± 0.0012 degrees at 90% of the sheet's transmittance. When at a distance of 60 cm and a transmittance of 90%, the axial resolution obtained using the 24-fields Böhler star in case of multi-frequency multi-path recovery $K = 1$, single-frequency $f_{min} = 20$ MHz and single-frequency $f_{max} = 120$ MHz are 0.4862 ± 0.1122 cm, 0.5610 ± 0.1122 cm, 0.5236 ± 0.1122 cm respectively. Consequently, we can conclude that using multiple frequencies yields improved axial/angular resolution.

4.4 Discussion

Four different experiments were conducted to study the effect of dust on 3D imaging systems. The sheet needs to be replaced with each data acquisition during the experiment. Multiple replacement operations will inevitably cause dust to fall off the sheet. Therefore, the light transmittance of the sheets may have changed slightly as the investigation progressed. Using a step-type me-

chanical adjustment device can avoid the imperceptible error generated by manual adjustment. In the case of the four-square target, the four squares are not absolutely flat. Therefore, using average depth values may already induce an error. These four squares can be replaced by industrially-manufactured squares with identical and flat surfaces. In the case of the Böhler star, we improved the lateral resolution by using multi-frequency estimation. Meanwhile, a similar effect had been observed in [36] when combining raw images at different exposures to obtain a high-dynamic-range (HRD) image. In [36], an adaptive HDR (AHDR) solution to the problem for the ToF case that overcomes the limited dynamic range of the system is proposed. When implementing AHDR method, the effective lateral resolution of the depth camera is increased by three times.

Compared with the single-frequency method (four-phases algorithm), the multi-frequency multipath recovery (matrix pencil method) can compensate for the effects of dirt to a certain extent. Nevertheless, the error still remains. We searched for the limit working conditions of a ToF camera in terms of varying light transmittance and distance. One way to improve the accuracy is to find the relationship between the real distance and the measured distance under different light transmittances through many experiments. This method can only be used in laboratories and is time-consuming and laborious. In a real-world scenarios this will not work due to the different and unknown reflectance of the targets. When the light transmittance of the sheet is less than 90%, the measurement result is already unreliable, but the accuracy of the camera can reach 99% in the range of 1.5 meters without the influence of dust. Thus, cleaning the protective cover of ToF cameras from excessive dust deposition when deployed in vehicles is shown to be necessary to ensure reliable operation. For example, in many car models, a high-pressure water column is used to wash the headlight outer cover to ensure that the lights and the associated sensors can work properly. A similar approach could be followed to minimize the effect of dust deposition on 3D sensors, such as ToF cameras, in vehicles.

5 Conclusions

In this paper, we investigated the effect of dirt on 3D imaging systems through several experiments using ten sheets with different transmittances between 50% and 100%. In the dirt-free environment, the 3D ToF camera has excellent performance, achieving 99.7% accuracy at a range of 1.5 m. As the camera cover was gradually covered by dirt, the performance of the 3D ToF camera dropped dramatically. Considering that ToF cameras are used in the field of autonomous driving, a clean cover is essential.

For each experimental target, we adopted both single-frequency estimation of a single path and multi-frequency estimation of several paths. Due to the presence of a secondary return path arising from the dirty sensor cover, the single-path assumption no longer holds. Multi-frequency methods were found to perform better than single-frequency methods for retrieving the true depth under the effect of dust, since they allow for distinguishing more than a single return path. The detailed performance of the 3D imaging system working with the range of 90% to 100% light transmittance of the protective cover can be studied in the future. The effect of different pollution sources on 3D imaging systems can be another future research direction.

Appendices

A Four-squares Target

Each square can be interpreted as a small white board experiment. In the case of multi-frequency multipath recovery with $K = 1$, 3D plots of the standard deviation of each small square versus ground-truth distance and transmittance are shown in Figure 31.

Figure 31: 3D plots of the standard deviation of each square versus ground-truth distance and transmittance.

Figure 32: Four-square target depth plots and its surface plots. The first column shows the depth plot and the surface plot when the camera works in the invalid work area (with 50% transmittance at 50 cm distance). The second column shows the depth plot and the surface plot when the camera works in the unreliable work area (with 85% transmittance at 50 cm distance). The third column shows the depth plot and the surface plot when the camera works in the reliable work area (with 100% transmittance at 50 cm distance).

The standard deviation plot of each small square is similar. Depending on the limit operating conditions of the camera in terms of varying light transmittance and distance, we divided the camera operation into three states in Figure 21(a) and Figure 21(b): the invalid work area, the unreliable work area, and the reliable work area. When the camera works in the invalid area, the depth estimation in Figure 32(a) is approximately equal to the distance between the camera and the sheet. The camera and the sheet are fixed so the distance between them is almost constant. Although the depth measurements are invalid, the variation in depth within each square is small, resulting in a very small standard deviation in the four subplots of Figure 31. Most of the standard deviations in the invalid area are about 1 mm. When the camera works in the unreliable work area, the depth estimation is unreliable. In Figure 32(b), the depth within each square varies significantly, which leads to an increase in the standard deviation in the unreliable work area. In the

four subplots of Figure 31, regions with standard deviations greater than 10 mm, which look like a mountain with a red peak, are concentrated in the unreliable working area. When the camera works in the reliable work area, the accuracy of the depth estimation is higher than 90%. In Figure 32(c), the depth variation is not apparent within each square, so the standard deviation is also within 1 mm in the reliable work area.

B Böhler Star

The axial and angular resolution are discussed when the camera works in the reliable work area. The axial resolution comparison of 24-fields stars and 48-fields stars in the case of single-frequency $f_{min} = 20\text{MHz}$, single-frequency $f_{max} = 120\text{MHz}$, multi-frequency multipath recovery with $K = 1$, multi-frequency multipath recovery with $K = 2$, path P_1 , respectively, is shown in Figure 33.

Figure 33: The first row shows axial resolution of 24-fields stars. The second row shows axial resolution of 48-fields stars.

The angular resolution comparison of 24-fields stars and 48-field stars in the case of single-frequency $f_{min} = 20\text{MHz}$, single-frequency $f_{max} = 120\text{MHz}$, multi-frequency multipath recovery with $K = 1$, multi-frequency multipath recovery with $K = 2$, path P_1 , respectively, is shown in Figure 34.

Figure 34: The first row shows angular resolution of 24-fields stars. The second row shows angular resolution of 48-fields stars.

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